

High photodetector responsivity and weak light detection in Manganese doped lead-free Low dimensional perovskite

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Photodetectors are optoelectronic devices commonly used in communication and sensing systems. Currently, commercial photodetectors using silicon and other inorganic semiconductors demonstrate high performance but are expensive, demand complex device manufacturing, and have limited sensitivity. This entails the need for the development of innovative photo-sensitive materials. In this vein, lead halide perovskites delivered competitive optoelectrical properties, however, the concerns of environmental toxicity and instability are potential barriers to practical deployment. Lead-free, environmentally benign perovskite alternatives with high responsivity and weak light detectability are advancing. We report a maximum photodetector responsivity for a bismuth-based perovskite by Mn²⁺ doping. The photodetector fabricated with a SnO₂ heterojunction also displayed reduced weak light detection as low as 49.1 nW cm⁻².

1. Introduction

Photodetectors are widely used to convert optical signals into analyzable electrical signals in various fields such as biomedical applications, military surveillance, the automation sector, optical communications, etc.¹ Through the process of the photoelectric effect, photodetectors capture the characteristics of incident light by converting the absorbed light energy into electrical signals or currents. Semiconducting materials are employed as active materials in the fabrication of photodetectors.² The applicability of a photodetector depends on factors such as photo-response speed, sensitivity to low illumination intensity detection, and dynamic range response. A photodetector's performance is assessed using several criteria, including response time, responsivity (R), noise current, external quantum efficiency, linear dynamic range (LDR), and specific detectivity (D^*).³⁻⁶ Commercial photodetectors currently use silicon and other inorganic semiconductors as the active layer, such as gallium phosphide, lead sulfide, etc. However, their expensive and complex manufacturing process as well as low sensitivity represent hurdles to achieving full versatility. Although solution-processable materials such as polymers and quantum dots have been proposed for photodetectors, their low light absorption and poor electrical performance are limiting their practical implementation.⁷

Lead halide perovskite has shown its potential not only in solar cells but also in photodetectors owing to its excellent optoelectronic properties such as unique light absorption, tuneable band gap, high carrier mobility, and long diffusion length.⁸⁻¹⁵ For instance, a fast response is achieved when

measuring a MAPbBr₃ single crystal on a silicon wafer within a detection range of 405–1064 nm.¹⁶ Compositional engineered lead halide perovskites have also been explored for photodetectors. Despite these remarkable achievements, Pb toxicity and material instability continue to pose challenges for their commercial efforts.^{12,14,17,18} To address these concerns, Pb-free perovskite, which can provide comparable performance to that of Pb-perovskites and stability of inorganic materials, is of paramount interest. Originating from the perovskite solar cell research, replacing divalent Pb with other elements such as Sn, Ge, Cu, Pd, Mn, Fe, Sb, and Bi is an attractive alternative.¹⁸⁻²³ Among them, Sn and Ge suffer from rapid oxidation and instability.^{18,20,21} Pb-substituted perovskite photodetectors with small active areas and the prerequisite of high illumination intensity have been identified as a major challenge in the military and industrial sectors. Thus, the development of Pb-free perovskite photodetectors with weak illumination and high responsivity is anticipated. Arguably, it will be widely employed in surveillance, and medical applications and is particularly suitable for indoor applications.

Recently, photodetectors based on Bi-based perovskites have been studied. The Bi³⁺-Ag⁺ based perovskite with a band gap in the range of 1.72–2.19 eV showed promise in photodetectors, although currently, it is ineffective in solar cells. The visible light photodetector displayed a responsivity of 0.14 A W⁻¹ at the wavelength of 445 nm.²⁴ Further, the CsBi₃I₁₀ thin film based perovskite detects red light with a responsivity of 21.8 A W⁻¹.²⁵ However, in most cases, weak illumination detectability becomes a significant problem for photodetectors based on Bi-based perovskites.

In our quest to develop a Pb-free inorganic perovskite-based photodetector with high responsivity, we synthesized Cs₃Bi₂Br₉ (CBBR) as a photoactive material. The non-toxic nature of Bi and the improved stability of the composition in ambient air are key factors in the selection of perovskite.^{12,13,22} The photodetector fabricated with CBBR offers competitive responsivity. For further optimization, we adapted a doping strategy with the transition metal cation Mn²⁺ and examined the changes in photoresponsivity. The addition of Mn²⁺ passivates the defects which in turn reduces the dark current and improves the photoresponsivity. The practical use of Cs₃Bi₂Br₉ film as a photodetector is complicated by the difficulty of depositing a high-quality defects-free thin film. Currently, the fabrication of photodetectors from Mn-doped Cs₃Bi₂Br₉ utilizing the vacuum-assisted thermal deposition method remains unexplored. To our knowledge, the fabricated photodetector achieved the highest photo-response for a Bi-perovskite based photodetector with D^* of 2.09×10¹³ Jones and relatively weak-illumination detectability.

2. Results and Discussions

We optimized the CBBR powder via Mn²⁺ doping at two different concentrations (detailed in the experimental section). We used electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy to detect and quantify the Mn²⁺ doping into perovskite. We used 25% and

50% of Mn^{2+} in the precursor ratio, and for readability convenience, hereafter we adopt the terminology of doped perovskites as 2Mn:CBBr and 5Mn:CBBr for 25% and 50% Mn^{2+} doped CBBr powders, respectively. Fig. S1 shows the X-band of EPR spectra collected at variable temperatures for the CBBr (control) and Mn-doped powders. The EPR spectrum of 2Mn:CBBr and 5Mn:CBBr (Fig. S1a) at room temperature substantiates the incorporation of Mn^{2+} into perovskite and shows a quasi-isotropic peak with partially resolved fine and hyperfine structures, while the pristine CBBr exhibits featureless spectrum. The calculated g value of 2.023 is slightly larger than the value expected for high-spin Mn^{2+} ions which suggests no orbital contributions to their magnetic moments in octahedral environments (${}^6A_{1g}$ term), and these ions are not completely magnetically isolated. We supported this hypothesis by improving the resolution of the EPR spectra that we acquired over variable temperatures ranging from 5 to 290 K (Fig. S1b). As expected, for a paramagnetic compound, the intensity of the signals increases as the temperature decreases. We noted that the centerline becomes more isotropic and the hyperfine structure signals gradually disappear with increasing temperature. However, not all signals obtained by the zero-field splitting disappear, suggesting that the distribution of Mn^{2+} ions is not completely homogeneous, and therefore magnetic interactions affect some but not all of them. We examined the difference in the EPR spectrum at room temperature obtained before and after measurements carried out at low temperatures (Fig. S1c). The manganese concentration has increased as the centerline has weak resolution through narrowing exchange. This suggests that the low temperature, or more likely, the applied magnetic field affects these measurements and modifies the distribution of Mn^{2+} ions. The number of unpaired spins per mg in the 5Mn:CBBr ($n = 1.78 \times 10^{18}$ spin/mg) is calculated by comparing the intensity of its EPR signal with that of a standard (copper sulfate); suggesting the determined weight percent of Mn^{2+} to be 3.2%. We used Raman spectroscopy together with the powder X-ray diffractograms to uncover the effect of Mn^{2+} inclusion. For 5Mn:CBBr and CBBr, the two strong Raman peaks

corresponding to the Bi-Br A_{1g} and E_g vibrational modes at 192 cm^{-1} and 167 cm^{-1} respectively can be observed (Figure S2).¹² Although no significant shift was detected, the peak intensities of 5Mn:CBBr increased compared to that of CBBr for all the Raman peaks, suggesting that the vibration coupling strength of BiBr₆ octahedra increased significantly in the presence of Mn^{2+} . We attribute this to the enhancement of octahedral compression, as a result of more stronger exciton-phonon interactions.^{12b} The powder diffraction patterns (Fig. 1) illustrate the P3m1 layered vacancy-ordered trigonal structure for both CBBr and Mn:CBBr powders.²⁶ The (1,0,1), (2,0,1), and (2,1,2) reflections from Mn:CBBr powder showed an untraditional peak shifting towards the lower angles gradually with an increasing amount of Mn in perovskite powder (Fig. 1b-e). This indicates an expansion of the lattice parameters, despite the lower ionic radii of Mn^{2+} and Mn^{3+} than those of Bi^{3+} and Cs^+ . However, compared to the CBBr powder, the XRD peak intensity and corresponding full width at half maximum (FWHM) increased slightly with increasing Mn doping (Fig. 1b-e). Increased peak intensity in the doped samples confirms the enhanced crystallinity.

Further, we extracted the average crystallite size and microstrain for pristine and Mn-doped powder from the Williamson–Hall (W–H) method (Fig. 1f, 1g, Fig. S3).²⁷ Higher micro-strain values are hypothesized to cause intrinsic degradation of polycrystalline perovskites as they have structural inhomogeneity due to the soft ionic nature of lattice. Additionally, strain-induced changes in grain size and crystal growth direction can cause disorders in grains and subgrains, which increases defect density, affects the quality of the thin film, and impacts device performance.^{27c}

The calculated microstrain from the slopes of the W–H plots has significantly decreased in Mn-doped powders. The microstrain decreased from 4.01×10^{-4} in the pure CBBr to 3.97×10^{-4} for 2Mn:CBBr and shows a further decrease to the lowest value of 2.57×10^{-4} for 5Mn:CBBr (Fig. 1g). On the other hand, the calculated average crystallite size slightly decreases from $\sim 200 \text{ nm}$ in CBBr to 170 nm for 2Mn:CBBr and $\sim 150 \text{ nm}$ in

Figure 1. (a) powder X-ray diffraction patterns of $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ with Mn doping. The zoom-in view of b) the (1,0,1), c) the (2,0,1), d) the (0,2,2), and e) the (2,1,2) reflections, (f) the Williamson-Hall plot of the CBBr, and (g) 5 Mn:CBBr, and (h) UV-Vis absorption spectra of the CBBr and the Mn:CBBr powders. The inset shows the zoom-in view of absorption onset and images of the synthesized powders.

5Mn:CBBr (Fig. 1f, 1g) suggesting the role of Mn doping in controlling the crystal growth and grain size.

The UV-vis absorption spectra from diffuse reflectance measurements (Fig. 1h) using the Kubelka-Munk function for the CBBr and Mn:CBBr powders as well as the optical images of the polycrystalline powders are shown in the inset. The absorption spectra of CBBr, and Mn:CBBr powders show a sharp excitonic absorption feature, which is due to bound excitons in the lattice and is related to the highly distorted structure of BiBr_6 octahedra. Upon Mn doping, the intensity of the exciton absorption peak increases with a slight band edge shift toward a longer wavelength peak centered at 460 nm (2.69 eV) compared to the original peak at 450 nm (2.75 eV); indicating the Mn dopant has the potential to tailor the optical properties of CBBr. The corresponding direct band gap calculated from the Tauc plot yields a value of 2.62 eV for the pristine and 2.60 for the 5Mn:CBBr (Fig. S4). The microstructure of the synthesized perovskite is presented in Fig. S5. Based on the detailed elemental and photo-physical studies of the perovskite powders, we selected the 5Mn:CBBr with reduced microstrain values as the target perovskite and compared the photodetector properties with the pristine CBBr as a control sample. Firstly, we deposited the thin films by vacuum-assisted thermal evaporation of the corresponding powders and were subject to annealing at 100 °C for one hour. Compact surfaces of thin film can be deduced from the SEM images (Figure 2a, 2b). The UV-Vis absorption spectra of CBBr and 5Mn:CBBr thin

films are plotted (Figure 2c), and the increase in absorption with doping can be attributed to the improved thin film quality, resulting in lower light scattering loss.²⁸ The optical band gap of the fabricated thin films is estimated to be 2.762 eV (CBBr) and 2.759 eV (5Mn:CBBr) from the Tauc plot (Figure 2d). We carried out space-charge-limited-current (SCLC) measurements to determine the trap density with and without Mn doping. Hole-only devices were fabricated with the structure ITO/PEDOT/perovskite/Spiro-OMeTAD/Ag, for pristine and 5Mn:CBBr, and the dark current-voltage characteristics of the devices are measured (Figures 2e and 2f). The trap density (N_t) of carriers is estimated using the below equation.¹⁵

$$N_t = \frac{2\varepsilon_0\varepsilon_r V_{\text{TFL}}}{qL^2} \quad (1)$$

where ε_0 represents the vacuum permittivity ($\varepsilon_0 = 8.86 \times 10^{-14}$ F cm⁻¹), q is the elementary charge ($q = 1.60 \times 10^{-19}$ C), L indicates the thickness of the perovskite thin film (~268 nm) and ε_r is the relative permittivity of the Bi-based perovskite.¹⁵ The trap density (N_t) is proportional to the V_{TFL} . The V_{TFL} of the pristine CBBr device decreases from 1.17 to 0.582V for 5Mn:CBBr based devices respectively, suggesting traps are filled with dopant ions. The lowest trap density is shown by Mn-doped samples, suggesting the addition of Mn passivates the defects and thus reduces leakage dark current in photodetector devices.

Figure 2. (a, b) SEM images of the $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ (CBBr) and 5Mn-CBBr film deposit by a vacuum-assisted thermal deposition method, (c) UV-vis absorbance spectra of the thin films, (d) Tauc plot of the fabricated films extracted from UV-vis spectra, and (e, f) SCLC measurements plot of pristine CBBr and 5Mn-CBBr based hole-only devices. Inset: cross-section SEM for hole-only devices.

We fabricated the photodetector based on the CBBr and the 5Mn:CBBr perovskites. The photo-response behaviors of the pristine CBBr and SnO₂/CBBr based p-n heterojunction are compared in Figure S6a. Figure S6b shows the schematic diagram of the two device structures employed. The photocurrent of the SnO₂/CBBr heterojunction device increases by two orders of magnitude compared with the pristine CBBr-based one. A large reverse leakage current is noted in the pristine photodetector device fabricated without hole-blocking layers. Mn-doping in CBBr thin films improves the device's performance, and Figure 3a, b presents the photo-response behavior curves of the SnO₂/CBBr heterojunction photodetector under different illumination intensities with and without the Mn²⁺ doping. Both photodetectors showed an excellent signal recognition ability. The Mn-doped photodetector performs better especially under weak light illumination, rising from a lower current density under dark conditions. We also measured the current density and voltage (*J-V*) characteristics of the photodetectors in the dark condition and under the illumination of 3.14 mW cm⁻² (Figure S7). The Mn-doped devices showed an inhibited dark current and improved photocurrent. Meanwhile, the optimized devices manifested a larger built-in electric field with light illumination, which contributes to effective carrier extraction. To demonstrate the weak light stability, device performance including Linear

Dynamic Range (LDR)^{29,30} and On/Off ratio³¹ was determined from

$$\text{LDR} = 20 \lg \left(\frac{P_{\max}}{P_{\min}} \right)$$

and

$$\frac{\text{On}}{\text{Off}} = \frac{J_{\text{light}} - J_{\text{dark}}}{J_{\text{dark}}}$$

The P_{\max} and P_{\min} represent the maximum and minimum incident light intensity, while the J_{light} and J_{dark} are the response current density under light and dark conditions. With Mn doping, the LDR of the devices increased remarkably from 95 to 139 dB (Fig. 3c) and benefited from improved sensitivity to weak light signal dump to 49.1 nW cm⁻². Meanwhile, the On/Off ratio increased in magnitude up to 10⁶-fold due to the suppressed dark current (Fig. S8). The dark current for photodetectors is mainly generated by the trapping/de-trapping process in defect states. The addition of Mn passivates the defects and causes further reduction of the dark current.³² The responsivity (R)³³ was estimated from and is plotted in Fig. 3d.

$$R = \frac{J_{\text{light}} - J_{\text{dark}}}{P_{\text{in}}}$$

Figure 3. Photodetection performance characterizations of the optimized SnO₂/Cs₃Bi₂Br₉ heterojunction photodetector (0 V bias) with and without Mn-doping, (a) I-t curves of a pristine device with a light modulation frequency of 0.5 Hz under various illumination intensities of 375 nm, (b) I-t curves of 5Mn-CBBr device, (c) LDR deduced by $J_{\text{light}}-P_{\text{in}}$ curves, (d) light intensity-dependent responsivity, (e) wavelength-dependent responsivity curves, (f) normalized frequency-dependent photocurrent curve for calculating -3 dB bandwidth, and (g) cycling curves at 0 V bias under continuous light irradiation at 375 nm 3.14 mW cm⁻².

The responsivity achieved up to 139.7 mA W⁻¹ under a weak light condition with Mn²⁺ doping, the highest value reported among Bi-based perovskite photodetectors (Table 1). Arguably, these photodetectors show a higher value of R under weak illumination because the photogenerated carriers extraction process dominates under weak light while quenching increases with stronger light.²⁸ We further analyzed the spectral dependence of photocurrent (Fig. 3e) and the photodetector exhibits excellent response in the ultraviolet-visible region (300–550 nm), and the highest responsivity is 43.1 mA W⁻¹ at 440 nm, suggesting that the SnO₂/CBBr heterojunction photodetector is suitable for imaging applications in the ultraviolet-visible range. The performance of the frequency response is characterized by tracking the photocurrent amplitude as magnifying the frequency of the On-and-Off cycle (Fig. 3f). When the On and Off-cycle times are faster than the response time of devices, maximum current decay is detected. The 3dB bandwidth (f_{-3dB}) is defined as the frequency at which the peak power attenuates to half of the initial value. Both types of photodetectors manifest similar frequency response

properties with f_{-3dB} of 6×10⁴ Hz, indicating fast signal response. Figure S9 shows the current spectral noise density of the device in the frequency range from 1 Hz to 2×10⁴ Hz. It was noted that the noise current is reduced by nearly two orders of magnitude. The reduced magnitude of noise can be explained by the suppressed 1/f noise due to the higher photo conductivity of the 5Mn:CBBr film. A 1/f noise behavior dominates the low-frequency part of the noise spectrum while a curve protuberating appears at a high frequency in the control device, resulting from the deep-level defect. Specific detectivity (D^*)³⁴ is a parameter for comprehensively assessing the performance of a photodetector, which can be determined by $D^* = R \times (A \times \Delta f)^{1/2} / i_n$, in which A is the active area (0.04 cm² in our study), i_n is the measured noise current and Δf is the electronic bandwidth. Owing to the improved R and the lower dark current, the D^* of the CBBr-based photodetectors improved from 7.78×10¹¹ to 8.63×10¹³ Jones. Furthermore, the inorganic Bi-based photodetectors displayed excellent cycling stability without apparent photocurrent reduction when exposed to 375 nm in ambient air (Fig. 3g).

Table 1: Comparative performance parameters of reported bismuth based perovskites photodetector and the present work

Device	Response range (nm)	LDR (dB)	Responsivity (mA·W ⁻¹)	Weak light detection limit (nW cm ⁻²)	Detectivity (Jones)	Ref.
NiO _x /Cs ₃ Bi ₂ Br ₉	300–550	116.6	4.33@0 V	~10 ³	1.3 × 10 ¹¹	[35]
MA ₃ Bi ₂ I ₉	300–600	NA	1.76@0 V		1.3 × 10 ¹²	[36]
TiO ₂ /Cs ₃ Bi ₂ Br ₉	300–550	128.6	6@0 V		3.39 × 10 ¹¹	[37]
SnO ₂ /Cs ₂ AgBiBr ₆	300–480	-	110@0 V	~100	2.1 × 10 ¹⁰	[38]
SnO ₂ /Cs ₃ Bi ₂ Br ₉	300–550	139	139.7@0 V	49.1	2.09×10 ¹³	This work

3. Experimental

Materials and methods

Materials were purchased from vendors and used as received. Dimethyl Sulfoxide and Chlorobenzene from Acros Organics, while Hydrobromic acid (48%) and Nitric Acid (70%) were obtained from Fisher. Spiro-OMeTAD obtained from Merck KGaA. Acetone and 2-propanol were obtained from Scharlau and absolute ethanol from Labkem. 4-tert-butylpyridine, and Bis(trifluoromethane) sulfonimide Lithium Salt obtained from Sigma Aldrich. Caesium bromide, Manganese (II) Bromide hydrate, and Bismuth (III) Bromide obtained from Thermo Scientific.

Synthesis of CBBr and Mn:CBBr perovskite powder

3 mmol of CsBr and 2 mmol of BiBr₃ precursors were weighed in separate vials. Desired amounts of MnBr₂·4H₂O (25 mol% and 50 mol% mol, relative to Bi) were weighed out and added to separate vials containing BiBr₃. 5 ml HBr aliquots were measured and transferred to vials containing BiBr₃. Mixtures were heated at 80 °C until fully dissolved. CsBr solutions in HBr were carefully added dropwise to respective BiBr₃ or Mn-doped BiBr₃ solutions. Upon addition of CsBr solutions, an immediate yellow precipitate occurred, which was cooled and filtered once the solution was cooled down and washed with ethanol. Finally,

the product was collected and dried at 40 °C under vacuum and stored in vials in desiccators.

Photodetector fabrication and characterization

The FTO-coated glass substrates were cleaned in sequential steps. A vertical device type architecture is used to fabricate the photodetector. The SnO₂ was deposited by spin-coating the hydrogels (purchased from Alfa Aesar and diluted with deionized water 3 times before use) at 3500 rpm for 30 s, followed by annealing at 150 °C for 45 min. The SnO₂ substrate was treated with UV-ozone for 60 min before use. The microcrystalline CBBr was thermally evaporated on the substrates with a vacuum pressure of 5 ×10⁻⁴ Pa. The top electrode was made with gold (Au) deposition using a thermal evaporator system. The photodetector was realized with the configuration of the FTO/SnO₂/CBBr/Au with an effective illuminated area of 0.04 cm² and the device architecture is shown in Figure S1. The I–V characteristics of the photodetector were measured using a Keithley electrometer (at a sweeping voltage of ±1 V with 0.001 intervals under dark and light conditions). An LED of 375 nm with tunable incident light intensity was used for the photoelectrical measurements. The spectral response of the photodetector was measured on an external quantum efficiency measurement system. All the measurements were made after exposure of the device to the atmosphere under ambient conditions.

Space Charge Limited Current

Hole-only and electron-only devices were fabricated using the following structures; Hole-only Device: FTO/PEDOT:PSS/perovskite/Spiro-OMeTAD/Ag. Electron-only Device: FTO/SnO₂/Perovskite/PCBM/Ag as reported previously.³⁹ In an Argon-filled glovebox, 0.52M solution of CBBr perovskite was prepared by dissolving CBBr in DMSO. CBBr solution was filtered using a 0.22µm hydrophobic PTFE filter. 50 ul of perovskite solution was spin-coated on the substrate following a 2-step process; Step 1: 1000 RPM, 500 RPMs⁻¹, 5 seconds Step 2: 5000 RPM, 2500 RPMs⁻¹, 25 seconds. During the second step, Chlorobenzene (0.1mL) was dripped onto substrates 20 seconds into the process. Substrates were immediately transferred to a hotplate at 150 °C to anneal at which point the perovskite film became yellow in color. After 15 minutes, substrates were removed and allowed to cool to room temperature.

Material characterization

RAMAN measurements were taken using a Renishaw InVia Raman spectrometer with a Leica DMLM microscope. Laser sources; 514 nm (ion-argon laser, Modu-Laser) and 785 nm (diode laser, Toptica). The spectrometer was previously calibrated with Ag (Ag 3d_{5/2}, 368.26 eV). UV-Vis spectra were recorded in diffuse reflectance mode using a Shimadzu UV-2600 spectrometer equipped with an integrating sphere (Shimadzu ISR-2600). The reflecting reference used was a barium sulfate pellet. Samples were diluted with barium sulfate powder for measurement; spectra were taken with different concentrations of sample to barium. Electron Paramagnetic Resonance (EPR) spectra were measured using a Bruker ELEXSYS E500 spectrometer operating at the X-band at room temperature and variable low temperature using an Oxford He-cryostat. The spectrometer was equipped with a superhigh-Q resonator ER-4123-SHQ. Perovskite powder was placed in quartz tubes and spectra were recorded using typical modulation amplitudes of 1.0 G at a frequency of 100 kHz and a microwave power of 200 mW. The magnetic field was calibrated by an NMR probe and the frequency inside the cavity (~9.4 GHz) was determined with an integrated MW-frequency counter. The Mn dopant concentration was evaluated by integrating the EPR spectrum twice and by comparing it with a standard CuSO₄·5H₂O sample. Data were collected and processed using the Bruker Xepr suite. X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) patterns were collected by using a PHILIPS X'PERT PRO automatic diffractometer operating at 40 kV and 40 mA, in theta-theta configuration, secondary monochromator with Cu-Kα radiation (λ = 1.5418 Å) and a PIXcel solid state detector (active length in 2θ 3.347°). Ultraviolet-visible spectrum of materials collected using a Cary 60 Ultraviolet-Visual spectrophotometer λ=1000-300 nm. Temperature-dependent X-ray Diffraction patterns (TD-XRD) were collected on perovskite films using a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer operating at 30 kV and 20 mA, equipped with a Cu tube (λ = 1.5418 Å), a Vantec-1 PSD detector, and an Anton Parr HTK2000 high-temperature furnace.

4. Conclusions

We synthesized lead-free bismuth-based perovskites and investigated the impact of Mn²⁺ doping on the structural, optical, and electrical properties. The addition of Mn²⁺ passivates the defects and reduces the dark current which improves the photoresponsivity. Thus, fabricated photodetector using Mn²⁺ doped Cs₃Bi₂Br₉ perovskite in a heterojunction with SnO₂ displayed reduced weak light detection as low as 49.1 nW cm⁻², with high sensitivity, and highest among the halide perovskite families. Particularly, from the perspective of environmentally benign materials, the Mn-doped Cs₃Bi₂Br based photodetectors are suited for indoor applications. This work validates and paves the way for lead-free perovskites for the fabrication of high-performance self-powered photodetectors.

Author Contributions

JHM carried out the synthesis and Materials characterization, SK and SA supervised it. MPU assisted JHM. LL made EPR characterization, ZL fabricated & characterized PDs and MW supervised it. S. K., S.A., directed the research. All authors contributed to the draft and prepared the final version.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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